

Psychological Challenges of Cyberspace: A Systematical Review of Meta-analysis

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Controlling the antisocial conduct of the younger generation requires a thorough understanding of the difficulties posed by psychological factors. Through this, the measurement for prevention and treatment lowers the unfavorable consequences of cyberspace. A scholarly paper that provides an overview of the psychological and behavioral challenges of virtual space does not exist. It is very important to highlight this new area for the younger generation's prevention. The PRISMA methodology was used for systematic reviews of meta-analysis. Data was collected from the Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE). That had 2904 documents. Sixteen documents were selected with the PRISMA rules. The data was analyzed using At list version 9 and Excel software for portraying the diagrams. The study discovered some evidence of psychological difficulties in cyberspace, including issues with family, motivation, and culture. The study provided evidence that the creation of cultures online has unintended consequences. Behavior modification Users' actions are altering negatively. Cyberspace demonstrated that users became disengaged from their tasks. Although the internet diminishes its users' dignity, the most complex situation is cyber sickness, which is worsening the problems for the users. Cyberspace separates users from the real world and keeps them occupied with fictitious circumstances in the virtual world. It is highly suggested that researchers highlight the negative effects of cyberspace and its side effects. The side effects of cyberspace must have awareness among the users.

Keywords: digital space, virtual space, virtual reality, obstacles, behavioral challenges, internet surfing, virtual milieu

The new era of digital technology introduced a new interface that is called "cyberspace." Even though this virtual reality has many pros, it also has cons. In particular, diagnosing the challenges of the psychological aspects of cyberspace is a very important topic for controlling the deviant behavior of the new generation. Through this, preventive and curative measures could be identified and take reasonable actions to reduce the negative and side effects of cyberspace.

Psychological challenges are mental and behavioral statuses that arise as obstacles in the normal process of psycho-cognitive processes (*What Is Psychological Challenges | IGI Global*, n.d.). Cyberspace is also known as digital space. It is a virtual reality platform for connecting, communicating, transacting, and working; teaching, leading, and informing. Concisely, almost all types of social interactions could take place in the soft form in the use of a technology called cyberspace. Lessig's (as cited by Černý, 2021) definition of cyberspace is a location on a digital platform. There are

inhabitants. They encounter all the same kinds of things that they encounter in actual space. Some people go through more. They encounter this in groups, in communities, with strangers, with people they get to know, and perhaps with people they like, rather than as lone players in a high-tech computer game.

As postulated by the research authors, cyberspace psychological challenges are those obstacles that are created due to the usage and surfing of digital space. Through this, it changes human behavior, mental processes, and the culture of cyberspace. Cyberspace has both positive and negative effects. Some researchers revealed a high level of psychological challenge and a propensity for neurotic states, including depression, anxiety, and obsessive-phobia (Kulikova et al., 2018). More than half of the experiment's participants were found to have shown neurotic tendencies (Kulikova et al., 2018). The significance of digital space and contemporary psychological obstacles; the authors emphasize the need to explore the metadata of psychological challenges in the use of cyberspace.

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Review of Literature

The Cyber-Physical-Physiological-Psychological-Socio-Mental Environment, also known as the CP3SME, is a multidimensional complex model that creates and evolves a variety of spaces for different kinds of people who interact with, reflect on, or influence one another through various links within space or through spaces (Zhuge, 2011). The most common psychological challenges are fear, embarrassment, isolation, and helplessness (ThickItBlogger, 2014). Some authors proved that cyberspace or digital space use was positively associated with both cyber bullying and cyber victimization (Khawrin et al., 2021). However, people should modify their conduct in business interactions to make better-informed decisions for training and selection, as well as for

individuals to strategically intervene to affect the cultural adaptation process and results (Molinsky, 2007).

According to research done in Ghana using data from the Global School-Based Health Survey (GSHS), senior high school students had a variety of psychosocial problems associated with engaging in cyberspace (N-yelbi et al., 2021). For example, 15% of them said they felt lonely, 13% said they were too anxious, and 38% said they felt depressed or hopeless. Moreover some university students face aggression, disobedience to authority, hyperactivity, disregard for the law, and any other type of disagreeable behavior (N-yelbi et al., 2021). People engaging in a technological environment are moving away from a culture that defines mainstream media and toward one where other forms of mediated experience are proliferating. In actuality, interaction is what defines cyberspace and is the foundation upon which a new sense of identity and community may be created (Riva & Galimberti, 1997).

The Internet's role as a contemporary communication medium and the exponential growth of information play a role in the development of psychological issues in young people, particularly when it comes to displaying negative emotional states such as depression, lowering levels of self-confidence and self-esteem, creating uncertainty, exhibiting signs of Internet addiction, and developing an obsessive need for virtual communication (Kulikova et al., 2018). Humans can remotely command the actuators to behave in physical space through cyberspace, and digital space users' actions can be detected and transmitted back to cyberspace for pattern analysis. This makes it possible for the internet to modify services in response to user input, as a change in behavior might be an indication of psychological development. For instance, this makes it possible for e-learning platforms to record how students behave while they are studying, allowing for real-time organization and modification of learning materials and procedures to improve learning efficiency. This has to do with categorizing student actions, including their facial expressions, and doing real-time analysis and modification (Zhuge, 2011). Cybersecurity, personal data, privacy, criminality, and irresponsibility are some additional challenges. Examining expert replies also helped define the categories for activities (Katharina. kiener-manu, 2019).

Research Gap

The virtual space has new emerging problems for internet users that alter their inner sound minds and behavioral systems. On the other hand, finding a generalized theme among academicians is a curial thing because there is no such thing as an academic article to give an overview of the psychological and behavioral obstacles of virtual space. This research could lead the next era of youngsters to become sound users of the internet and digital devices. Therefore, it is very important to scrutinize the psychological challenges of cyberspace.

Research Questions

What are the psychological challenges of cyberspace?

Objective of the Study

To find psychological challenges of cyberspace.

Method

Academic research methodology is an important roadmap for new learners. This footprint paves the way for further research and authentication of the data. Following the method rigorously, anyone

can diagnose the problems similarly. There are four steps to follow for equal findings via research method, research tool, data collection, and data analysis tool. This study followed these stages, as explained below.

Research Method

This is qualitative research with the new method called PRISMA. PRISMA stands for "Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses" (Pahlevan-Sharif et al., 2019). This technique gives an overall academic understanding of the systematic reviews of meta-analysis.

Measure

On July 14, 2022, the Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE) (<https://www.base-search.net/Search/Advanced>) research tool with an advanced option was selected for the data collection. After searching, 2904 documents were found.

Data Collection

The research data collection was based on a systematic, organized, and classified selection of keywords related to psychological challenges in cyberspace. For completion of this task, the BASE keywords were searched for psychology, psychological, challenges, problems, obstacles, cyberspace, digital space, the internet, and virtual space. The search fields in the BASE search engine were limited to the titles of the records for the period of 2010–2022. In addition, the worldwide open access content was selected. For consistency and filtering purposes, the search excluded books, book parts, conference objects, reviews, course material, lectures, manuscripts, patents, theses, musical notation, maps, audio, images, video, software, datasets, and unknown. The selection option was article contribution and report with reuse terms.

Inclusion Criteria

Scope: Worldwide

Period: 2010–July 2022

Language: English

Quality: academic published articles and reports.

There were 2904 documents and 2286 documents marked as ineligible by automation tools as mentioned above-excluded options. For excluding non-English language documents, 270 documents out of 618 were excluded. Furthermore, 364 records were screened to exclude the duplication and retrieval of the documents. As a result, 99 documents were excluded for having a duplicate and not retrieving the full documents. Finally, 233 documents were excluded that were not appropriate to the objectives of the research, and the remaining 16 documents were appropriate with the PRISMA rules selection technique as portrayed in Figure 1.

Data Analysis

The qualitative data were analyzed with inductive content analysis through Atli.ti version 9 and Excel software for portraying the diagrams. For analyzing the data, every article was searched to select the codes appropriate for the objectives of the study. The first codes were generated, and similar codes were joined with one theme. This provides a complete picture of the variables and indicators of the present study.

To ensure reliability, members of the research team independently analyzed the data. Everyone made codes and then themes for comparison. The results and findings of this data are generable from

the selected sample papers of the present study. In addition, the research triangulation was also processed for the validity and quality of the data. Three types of triangulation approaches, which were method, data collection, and data analysis, were employed in this study.

Figure 1

PRISMA Diagram

Results

For answering the above mentioned questions.

Table 1 shows the descriptive data of selected 16 articles, with their authors, the title of the article, and publication year.

Table 2 shows psychological problems caused by cyberspace. There are four themes with related codes. Which are defined as below.

Cyber and Family

Cyber and family themes had three codes, such as cyberspace for children's gaming, effect on children's parental control, and parental control challenges. The researchers' evidence showed that cyberspace has a very negative effect on the family system. Geležinienė, Melienė, and Vaitkevičienė (2015) argued that children "perceive parental control with regard to their online activities as strict and assertive" (pp. 377-378). However, this kind of perception differs between boys and girls in the family. Boys, for example, are inclined to the perception that parental control is stricter for them than it is for girls. In supporting this, Geležinienė, Melienė, and Vaitkevičienė (2015) in their study found that "boys were more inclined than girls to rate each statement about parental control giving higher estimate" (p. 378). This implies that for boys, parental control is perceived to be assertive, whereas for girls, parental control is perceived as a means of making them more obedient. For that reason, Geležinienė, Melienė, and Vaitkevičienė (2015) argue that "girls are just more obedient and take monitoring and control for granted."

Cyber Motivation

The second theme is cyber motivation, which has two codes of cyber and motivation and cyber space intimacy. Some researchers, such as Mogonea and Mogonea (2019) argued that "lack of motivation" influence the use of cyber space. Regarding cyber space intimacy, it

is argued that as the amount of closeness in cyberspace rises, the personal space distance will remain constant, however it will get shorter as the level of intimacy rises in physical space. This is in line with Nishihara and Okubo (2015) who argue, "The distance of the personal space in virtual space will not short even as the intimacy level increases, although the one in real space is considered short as the intimacy level increases."

Cyber and Culture

The third theme is about cyber and culture, which had two codes, namely cyber and culture; and cyber and intercultural differences. Cyberspace has an influence on cultures whereby some of them seem to be destructive and may be transferred to the real environment. For example, in a virtual space, individuals can informally form their own identities, which are different from those known and used in the real world. The persistence of such behavior affects cultural development, especially for the young stars. Some researchers such as Vilija Targamadžė and Tatjana Bulajeva (2018) noticed that the use of informal identity "affect young people subculture developments." Mogonea and Mogonea (2019) add that such a behavior leads into "risk of conflicts due to intercultural differences."

Behavioral Change

The fourth theme discussed behavioral change, which also has behavioral change and cyber eccentricity codes. Cyberspace use tends to affect the behaviors of its users. The deviant behavior due to cyberspace use is more noticeable among children and adolescents. A study by Targamadžė and Bulajeva (2018) revealed, "Behavior changes are seen in the way the teenagers communicate with adults (teachers, parents). It is understandable that in the virtual networks the age of people you are networking with does not matter." This kind of behavior is imported from cyberspace to the real environment.

Another behavioral change associated with cyberspace use is aggressiveness acquired from playing virtual games. Targamadžė and Bulajeva (2018) argue that when teenagers play virtual games on the internet:

Learn the aggressive style of behavior and overtake the model of communication culture. They are often reckless, aggressive and fight when they want to defend themselves. ...expert mentions that within the new generation group one may see a different teenager subgroup, which he describes as rebels. They actually demonstrate a narcissistic behavior and are forming a subculture that educators are worried about...the means they use to draw the attention to themselves are not adequate in photos they put in the Internet. ..Boys demonstrate their physical strength, socially unacceptable behavior, use of alcohol and drugs; girls demonstrate their outer beauty: excessive use of make-up, unacceptable and strange looking dressing style (pp. 49-51).

Figure 2 shows four themes of psychological challenges from five articles. Cyber and family themes have seven codes from the "Children and adolescents in virtual space: girls' and boys' behavior and attitude to parental control" article (Geležiniene et al., 2015). The cyber motivation theme has two codes from the "A Study on Personal Space in Virtual Space Based on Personality" (Nishihara & Okubo, 2015); and "From Traditional Classroom Communication to Communication in Virtual Space" article (Mogonea & Mogonea, 2019).

Table 1*Descriptive Data of Selected Documents*

No	Author/s	Topic	Year
1	Ryota Nishihara, Masashi Okubo	A study on personal space in virtual space based on personality	2015
2	Katiuscia Sacco, Irene Ronga, Pasqualina Perna, Alessandro Cicerale, Elena Del Fante, Pietro Sarasso, Giuliano Carlo Geminiani	A virtual navigation training promotes the remapping of space in all centric coordinates: evidence from behavioral and neuroimaging data	2022
3	Wookhyun Park, Woong Choi, Hanjin Jo, Geonhui Lee, Jaehyo Kim	Analysis of control characteristics between dominant and non-dominant hands by transient responses of circular tracking movements in 3d virtual reality space	2020
4	Smitha Nayak, Mendon Suhan, Raveendranath Nayak, Cristi Spulbar, Ramona Birau, Sangam Mahesh Gull	Antecedents to purchase intention in virtual market space in india: an empirical investigation	2022
5	Lijia Zeng, Xiang Dong	Artistic style conversion based on 5g virtual reality and virtual reality visual space	2021
6	Tatyana V. Evsyukova, Susanna R. Agababyan, Evgeniya V. Kotelnikova, Tatyana M. Germasheva	Axiological world picture of the virtual language personality in blog-discourse space	2017
7	Renata Geležinienė, Rita Melienė, Asta Vaitkevičienė	Children and adolescents in virtual space girls' and boys' behavior and attitude to parental control	2015
8	Meytal Wilf, Mouna Cerra Cheraka, Max Jeanneret, Renaud Ott, Henri Perrin, Sonia Crottaz-Herbette, Andrea Serino	Combined virtual reality and haptic robotics induce space and movement invariant sensorimotor adaptation	2021
9	Kostas Mouratidisa, Ramzi Hassanb	Contemporary versus traditional styles in architecture and public space: a virtual reality study with 360-degree videos	2020
10	Kathy O'flynn-Magee, Elizabeth J. Straus, Aneet Dhaliwal, Samantha-Ruth Chande, Batool Alref, Prabhjot Randhawa, Yenlinh Chung, Salwa Khader	Creativity in a covid-19 virtual learning space	2021
11	Ernesto Cordero Collo, Jr.	Discovering the lived experiences of graduate students in the virtual space: reflections and lessons from a phenomenological inquiry	2021
12	Florentin Remus Mogonea, Florentina Mogonea	From traditional classroom communication to communication in the virtual space	2019
13	Jeffrey I. Gold, Nicole E. Mahrer,	Is virtual reality ready for prime time in the medical space? A randomized control trial of pediatric virtual reality for acute procedural pain management	2018
14	Vilija Targamadzė, Tatjana Bulajeva	New generation subculture formation on the crossing of real and virtual space	2017
15	Ana Alina Ionescu Dumitrache, Océane Rivoire	Protecting dignity in virtual space	2017
16	Tatiana D. Martsinkovskaya	The person in transitive and virtual space: new challenges of modality	2019

Table 2*Descriptive Data of Themes with its Codes*

No	Themes	Codes	Frequency	Total
1	Cyber and family	Cyber space for children gaming	1	7
		Effect to child parental control	2	
		Parental control challenges	4	
2	Cyber motivation	Cyber and motivation	1	2
		Cyberspace intimacy	1	
3	Cyber and culture	Cyber and culture	1	2
		Cyber and intercultural differences	1	
4	Behavioral change	Behavior change	3	4
		Cyber eccentricity	1	

Cyber and culture theme also has two codes from “From traditional classroom communication to communication in the virtual space” (Mogonea & Mogonea, 2019) and “New generation subculture formation on the crossing of real and virtual space” article (Targamadzė & Bulajeva, 2018). Lastly, behavioral change has four

codes from the “New generation subculture formation on the crossing of real and virtual space” (Targamadzė & Bulajeva, 2018); and “Combined virtual reality and haptic robotics induce space and movement invariant sensorimotor adaptation” article (Wilf et al., 2021).

Figure 2
Sankey Diagram Showing Themes and Articles

Table 3
Descriptive Data of Psychological Challenges

No	Codes	Frequency	No	Codes	Frequency
1	confidence in the use of cyber space	1	6	cyber space bullying	1
2	cyber and attention	1	7	cyber sickness	9
3	cyber and dignity	1	8	fatigue	2
4	cyber axiological impact	1	9	Cyber isolation	3
5	cyber reality and deception	2			

Table 3 depicts the psychological deviant behavior that is formulated by digital space usage. These deviant behaviors have a side effect on the cognition of the cyber users.

Confidence in the Use of Cyber Space

Internet users increase their confidence in the digital space that is credible along with providing hedonic choices. Credible cyber space with strengthened hedonic and utilitarian values tends to influence users psychologically in the decision-making process. Researchers such as Nayak, Suhan, Nayak, Spulbar, Birau, and Gull (Nayak et al., 2022) argued, “Confidence in apparel fit, utilitarian value, and hedonic value in strengthening the purchase intention of an online shopper.”

Cyber and Attention

Most cyber users cannot give attention to a specific objective. Similarly, Mogonea and Mogonea (2019) researches said, “Students may not be paying attention to the lesson.”

Cyber and Dignity

Human dignity as a fundamental right should be protected. Ways of protecting this right, particularly in the age of digitalization, have to be found. Some users lose their honor and respect because some users misuse the digital world for the wrong purposes. Dumitrache and Rivoire (2017) argue that “Human dignity in the digital age is being contested very openly today, and the Universal declaration of

Human Rights (1948) must update every time because of new ways of abuses... right in the particular space of virtual life, space which became more and more conducive to abuses of dignity.”

Cyber Axiological Impact

Some cyber users become victimized, and they are devalued by others. The vulnerability of being victimized becomes higher as one uses cyberspace for axiological needs. As quoted by Evsyukova, Agababyan, Kotelnikova, and Germasheva (2017) researches “ the indication of the vulnerability of the blog communicant personality needs include needs of self-identification, self-presentation, self-realization, the formation of self-concept in virtual communicative environment and the realization of the axiological picture of the world of virtual language personality.”

Cyber Reality and Deception

Sometimes, people post unrealistic information on digital platforms to deceive others. Deception, in many cases, has caused digital information users psychological problems. An example of cyber deception is portrayed by Wilf, Cheraka, Jeanneret, Ott, Perrin, Crottaz-Herbette, and Serino (Wilf et al., 2021) in this regard, they have this to conclude: “Surprisingly, in the robotically-guided condition, participants were not aware of the mismatch between the position of their real hand, as signaled by proprioception, and that of the virtual hand, as signaled by vision.”

Cyber Space Bullying

Cyber users face bullying resulting from negative emotions leads to unhealthy psychological well-being. Targamadzè and Bulajeva (2018) asserts that “stressing the importance of emotions in communication this expert also points out to virtual bullying. If it takes place, it spreads in the network very rapidly and then its impact is very strong.”

Cyber Sickness

Psychological well-being is the most important and this entity is the most vulnerable through cyberspace, which leads to cyber illness and cyber sickness. As Mouratidisa and Hassanb (2020) argue, “cyber sickness is an affection common to users of virtual environments. Similar in symptoms to motion sickness, cyber sickness can result in nausea, headaches, and dizziness.”

Fatigue

Cyber space causes psychological fatigue to cyber space users especially when they spend much more time in cyber space. In a study conducted by Gold and Mahrer (2018) they found that “the time for experimenting with virtual reality equipment should be controlled within 25 minutes as much as possible; otherwise, fatigue may occur.”

Cyber Isolation

Cyberspace users who spend too much time engaged in discussions and browsing cause emotions of loneliness to friends, family, and classmates accompanying them. This stops physical interactions between them. As Collo (2022) quoted that “there are no physical interactions between students and teachers. This often results in a sense of isolation for the students.”

Figure 3
Cyber Challenges Reported Frequencies

Figure 3 depicts the cyber challenges with the intensity of frequency reported and documented by the academic research authors. There are nine psychological challenges, which are generated by surfing cyberspace with unnecessary needs.

- What are the psychological challenges of cyberspace?

The study found some evidence that proved that there are many types of psychological challenges in cyberspace for its users. First dimension cyber and family issues; cyberspace problems for children's gaming, the side effects on children's parental control and the parental control system; there was positive evidence regarding the cyber and family problems. Second is the dimension of cyber motivation, which consists of cyber motivation and cyberspace intimacy. Some students lost their motivation when using the digital space, and even some spouses faced problems with motivation. The third dimension is cyber and culture, or cyber and intercultural differences. The research showed evidence that cyberspace has a side effect on culture formation. The fourth dimension is behavioral change. It also had two small parts: behavior change and cyber eccentricity. It is also proven that because of cyberspace, the behavior of users is changing negatively.

Furthermore, cyberspace is negatively changing the confidence of digital users in the blog users' demands. Cyberspace showed that the users lost attention while performing a task. Even though cyberspace degrades the dignity of its users, it also negatively affects axiological issues. Moreover, cyber virtual reality deceives users. Bullying is also found in cyberspace. The most sophisticated case was cyber sickness, which is causing more problems for the users. Even though it fatigues them. Besides that, cyberspace isolates the users from the physical world and makes them busy in the virtual world in an imaginary situation.

Discussion

The findings of this study found that the use of cyberspace contributes to psychological problems. Cyberspace psychological problems that were found in this study were affecting different families especially when it comes child-parental control issues; motivation; and culture when some of the imported deviant behaviors were brought into real environment. In this regard, the study provided evidence that the creation of cultures online has unintended consequences in the real environment. Moreover,

cyberspace influences behavioral modification to Users' actions negatively. Similarly, some authors also proved that some cyberspace users developed isolation, loneliness, and aggression (N-yelbi et al., 2021; ThickIt-Blogger, 2014). Moreover, some authors statistically proved that other psychological obstacles such as cyberbullying also take place (Khawrin et al., 2021).

Suggestion

It is highly suggested that researchers highlight the negative effects of cyberspace and its side effects because most researchers just see the positive behavior of cyber surfing. Moreover, a virtual milieu should be used as per the needs of humans. However, research on the psychological opportunities of cyberspace is recommended to have new academic pieces of evidence.

Every family must take care of one another. Do not allow a person to use digital space without necessity. Cyberspace changes the studying motivation, changes human behavior negatively, loses the attention of the students, human value is degraded, loses dignity, cyber bullying, cyber sickness, isolated and changes the culture, therefore, the side effects of cyberspace must have awareness the users.

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